

Security in Access Networks Using Visible Light Communications (VLC - LiFi) with Applications in a Hospital Setting

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Abstract

Visible light communication “VLC” is a communication medium that is currently evolving and improving the quality of INTERNET transmission. Li-Fi is the term used to label fast, low-cost wireless communications systems such as “VLC”.

Li-Fi has proven to be much faster than other data transmission systems known today, it is considered an ecological technology as it does not contaminate with radio frequencies, making it safer for the application of this technology in different places such as (Banks, Hospitals, Airports, ETC)

The project consists of improving the access network in different places in order to provide an alternative at a security level for the end user. The application was carried out within a hospital room and within a bank to see the differences that exist at the security level.

Keywords: VLC, LIFI, IOT, hospital network

I. INTRODUCCIÓN

The evolution of access networks has been a continuous process driven by the need for greater speeds, capacity, and efficiency in data transmission. Here is a summary of the main stages of this evolution:

Wireless Access Networks

Wi-Fi: Enabled wireless connectivity within local areas such as homes and offices. Evolution has led to faster standards such as Wi-Fi 4, 5, and 6, with speeds exceeding 1 Gbps.

Mobile networks (2G, 3G, 4G, 5G): Each generation has improved speeds and capabilities. 5G, for example, offers speeds of up to 10 Gbps and very low latencies.

Fiber Optic Networks

FTTx (Fiber to the x): Technologies such as FTTH (Fiber to the Home) and FTTB (Fiber to the Building) have brought optical fiber directly to homes and buildings, allowing for gigabit-per-second speeds.

GPON (Gigabit Passive Optical Network): A technology that allows multiple users to share a single optical fiber without the need for active components in the network, improving efficiency and reducing costs.

Visible light communications (VLC), VLC is the name given to an optical wireless communication system that carries information by modulating light in the visible spectrum (400 – 700 nm) which is mostly used for lighting. The communications signal is encoded by light. Interest in VLC has grown rapidly with the development of high-power light-emitting diodes (LEDs) in the visible spectrum. The motivation for using illumination light for communication is to economize energy by exploiting illumination to carry information and, at the same time, use newly applied technology as opposed to radio frequency (RF) technology, while using the existing infrastructure of lighting systems. The need to develop additional wireless communication technology is a result of the exponential growth in demand for high-speed wireless connectivity. Emerging applications utilizing VLC include:

- a) Indoor communication where there is an increasing demand for WiFi and cellular wireless communications following the smart city concept.
- b) Wireless communication link for the Internet of Things (IOT).
- c) Access communication systems as an intelligent part of transportation systems (ITS).
- d) Wireless communication systems in hospitals.
- e) Toys and theme park entertainment.
- f) Provision of dynamic advertising information through a camera on a smart phone.

II. BASIC CONCEPTS

Visible Light Communications (VLC) is a communication medium that is currently evolving and improving the quality of INTERNET transmission. Today, Li-Fi is the term used to label fast and low-cost wireless communication systems (such as VLC).

Li-Fi has a great advantage in that it can be used in areas sensitive to electromagnetic radiation such as: hospitals, airplanes, airports, etc., since it does not work with radio frequency. This technology has proven to be much faster than other data transmission systems known today, apart from being an ecological idea, VLC does not pollute with radio frequencies and makes it safer for the application of this technology in places where the implementation of RF Wi-Fi networks is generally not possible.

Figure 1: Principle diagram

Project problems and solutions

In Bolivia, as in any other country, computer security is important. For this reason, VLC can provide an alternative to this aspect. In this project, the application was carried out in a hospital and a bank to see the security levels that VLC meets in the access network of the same.

III. Li Fi Technology

Li-Fi is a high-speed wireless communication technology based on the transmission of information through the visible light spectrum. Its mentor was engineer Harald Haas (CEO of PureLiFi), who first referred to this technology at the TED conference held on September 15, 2011 in London.

VLC transmits information wirelessly by modulating the intensity of visible light. The technology is very useful for point-to-point communications, as a replacement for a physical cable. Li-Fi, unlike VLC, describes a complete wireless connectivity system as it offers bidirectional and multi-user connectivity (such as point-to-multipoint or multipoint-to-point configurations) and the possibility of having multiple network access points, forming a wireless network composed of small optical cells that provide the possibility of handover (seamless connectivity between cells) which enables the possibility of having mobile connectivity.

The IEEE 802.15.7 standard

Li-Fi technology, like VLC, operates under the IEEE 802.15.7 standard for OWC technologies. This standard defines several fundamental layers: a physical layer (PHY), which includes the optical transceiver, and a MAC layer, which provides access to the optical medium or channel. Several additional layers are also included in the architecture definition. Let's look at their characteristics.

Figure 2: Architecture of an IEEE 802.15.7 device.

Implementation Architecture

As seen by reviewing the information described in the IEEE 802.15.7 standard, Li-Fi technology can be implemented in both indoor and outdoor environments; and the coverage area is subject to the deployment of the transducer devices and, of course, to the requirements of each particular implementation. As an example, the figure shows a basic implementation diagram of the technology where all the devices involved appear.

Figure 3: Architecture of a Li-Fi network

The architecture in the figure represents an implementation where the information comes from the Internet or from an application running on a local server and is transmitted in streaming format to the clients; it would correspond to a point-to-multipoint “broadcast” type architecture where information is transmitted from a single access point to several clients. This information could be, for example, multimedia files such as a video file, a music file or a photograph. In this example, each client is receiving a different multimedia file at the same time.

VLC modulation methods

There are various modulation methods to encapsulate time-domain information in the context of VLC. The main difference between conventional communication scenarios and VLC is the requirement to maintain adequate communication performance, along with the need to attenuate the light intensity. These include:

- OOK (On Off Keying)
- PPM (Pulse Position Modulation)

International standards according to WHO and ITU for LIFI

Series H: Audiovisual and multimedia systems

Within this series, there are all the series subgroups related to the PAN (Personal Area Network) network, ranging from H.820 – H.859. PAN is the network access used in VLC technology.

Within the H series, the most important ones related to this project will be mentioned.

- H.835: conformance of ITU-T H.810 personal health devices: WAN interfaces part 5: PDC-01 HL7 messages sender.
- H.845.6: conformance of ITU-T H.810 personal health devices: PAN/LAN/TAN interface Part 5F: cardiovascular fitness and activity monitor Agent.
- H-845.14: Conformance of ITU-T H.810 personal health devices: PAN/LAN/TAN

IV. Project development

Li Fi Design

Below is a very simplified diagram of the network that already includes Li FI technology to the network for the specific areas.

Figure 4: University Hospital Data Center.

Luminosity in critical areas.

The following equation determines the luminosity calculation for all areas where the project needs to be applied:

$$\Phi_T = \frac{E_m * S}{C_u * C_m} \tau$$

Ecuación 1

Where:

Em = average lighting level (in LUX)

Φ_T = luminous flux that a certain room or area needs (in LUMENS)

S = surface to be illuminated (in m2).

Cu = Utilization coefficient. It is the ratio between the luminous flux received by a body and the flux emitted by the light source. It is provided by the luminaire manufacturer.

Cm = Maintenance coefficient. It is the quotient that indicates the degree of conservation of a luminaire

Selection of areas within the hospital

Figure 5: Operating room II of the Hospital

Network Traffic Sizing

For the sizing of the bandwidth required for the backbone, the following methodology is used: where the estimated theoretical calculation is carried out according to the user applications to determine an approximate bandwidth value.

Área de quirófano		
Usuario		Ancho de banda en Kbps
Quirófano I	Pc1	2133.33
Quirófano II	Pc2	2133.33
Sala de partos	Pc3	2133.33
	Suma	6399.99
Área de imagenología		
Usuario		Ancho de banda en Kbps
Tomografía	Pc1	1760
Ecografía	Pc2	1760
Rayos X I	Pc3	1760
Rayos X II	Pc4	1760
Mamografía	Pc5	1760
Laboratorio	Pc6	1760
Electroencefalografía	Pc7	1760
Electrocardiografía	Pc8	1760
	Suma	14080

Table 1: Bandwidth estimation for operating room and imaging areas within the hospital

3.5. *Wired network connection*

For the connection of the LiFi equipment, it will be done through the structural cabling system already existing in the University Hospital, connecting the GEOLIFI LED CW12 ROUND equipment to the access points that go to the nearest communications room. The equipment used has PoE (Power

over Ethernet) technology, which means that the UTP category 6 EIA/TIA 568-B cable will be used.

All this implementation of the LiFi equipment will be with the implementation of the WiFi network that the University Hospital already plans to implement.

Next, a preliminary plan will be made showing the plan of the third and fourth floors of the University Hospital, where you can see the distributed wiring, the location of the telecommunications cabinet and the computers or workstations where the LiFi equipment is located.

In the Telecommunications Cabinet there are: UTP category 7 cables, the router, the switch and the network server.

Figure 6: Preliminary plan of the distribution of wiring and LiFi equipment within the hospital

Network design for a Bank:

To design a network in a bank using Li-Fi technology, several key aspects must be considered to ensure that the network is secure, efficient and able to handle the specific needs of the banking environment. A detailed outline for the design of a banking network using Li-Fi is outlined below:

V. Results and discussion

Simulation results

Using MATLAB software, the optical power distribution was simulated to calculate the optical power distribution LOS (line of sight), link to receive plane of the localized areas.

	Parámetros	Valores
Sala	Tamaño	1 x 0,55 x 2,65 m ³
Fuente	Localización (1 LEDS)	(0,5 0,27 1,32)
	semiángulo a media potencia (FWHM1)	60
	Potencia transmitida (por LED)	1W
	centro de la intensidad luminosa	3845 - 4245 lx
Recepción	Recepción del plano por encima del piso	0.85 m
	Area activa (AR)	1 cm ²
	Mitad de angulo (FOV)	60
	Elevacion	90
	Azimut	0
	Δ_t	0.5 ns

Table 3: Parameters taken for the simulation.

Figure 7: Distribution of optical energy in the received optical plane for the operating room area within the hospital

In the figure, it can be observed that there is an almost uniform distribution of the optical power in the center with a maximum power of -15.87 dBm and a minimum power of -16.30 dBm.

The simulation was done within the operating room area, both for operating room I, operating room II, and delivery room with technical specifications of LiFi equipment from the company Oledcomm.

VLC Data Security

RPKI (Resource Public Key Infrastructure) is a public key infrastructure used to ensure the authenticity and integrity of Internet routes by cryptographically verifying network prefixes. Although RPKI is specifically designed for Internet route security and not for local networks or access technologies such as Li-Fi, some RPKI security principles and practices can be adapted to strengthen security in a Li-Fi environment.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

For the design, variables of lighting technology, modulation technique, performance and optical power were taken into account, where based on these variables it was possible to determine which Li-Fi equipment is best suited in the selected areas.

It was decided to use the Ethernet cable with the technology (PoE) in the Li-Fi equipment because the Hospital in La Paz Bolivia has structured cabling, but not enough to reach the Li-Fi equipment.

Implementing Li-Fi in a bank requires careful planning and effective integration with the existing network infrastructure. With the benefits of high speed, security and interference reduction, Li-Fi can significantly transform connectivity and operational efficiency in the banking environment.

A project of a secure optical communications system (VLC) is presented as a pioneer in the research and application of IOT technology, where a lot of information was collected for the analysis, design and development of this project.

Using RPKI for Internet routing security, its principles of authentication, integrity verification and access control can be adapted to strengthen security in a Li-Fi network, providing a robust and secure solution for sensitive environments such as banks.

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